

Event metadata

Event title	MetaboLights: the home for metabolomics experiments and derived information
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	09/04/2024
Time of event	4pm AEST
Topic description	<p>MetaboLights is an open-access database for metabolomics studies, their raw experimental data and associated metadata. It is cross-species, cross-technique and covers metabolite structures and their reference spectra as well as their biological roles and locations where available. MetaboLights is the recommended metabolomics repository for a number of leading journals and ELIXIR, the European infrastructure for life science information.</p> <p>This webinar will provide an introduction to MetaboLights and how it can be used as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A repository, enabling the metabolomics community to share findings, data and protocols from metabolomics studies. • A compound library of curated knowledge about metabolite structures, their reference spectra, as well as their biological roles, locations, concentrations, and raw data from metabolic experiments. <p>The webinar will provide details about data availability, standards and re-use, as well as guidance on submitting your own metabolomics data.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/metabolights
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless

	otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Metabolomics Metabolites Data sharing
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists and bioinformaticians who are working with metabolomics data. Perhaps you have your own data to share or you are seeking information about metabolites and biological roles.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe how MetaboLights can be used as a repository, enabling the metabolomics community to share findings, data and protocols from metabolomics studies. • Describe how MetaboLights can be used as a compound library of curated knowledge about metabolite structures, their reference spectra, as well as their biological roles, locations, concentrations, and raw data from metabolic experiments.
Speakers	Dr Thomas Payne, Scientific Database Curator - MetaboLights, EMBL-EBI
Related material	None